

*environmental
directions*

The NERC Mission

The mission of the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) is to advance knowledge, understanding and prediction of the environment and natural resources.

NERC is the lead UK body for basic, strategic and applied environmental research.

In fulfilling its mission the Council has seven Strategic Aims

- fostering research and technology development aimed at understanding and predicting environmental processes
- education, training and maintaining core excellence in basic and strategic science
- collecting, curating, interpreting and supplying environmental data
- providing objective, independent expert advice and information
- developing and using technologies and maintaining scientific facilities
- ensuring linkage with the user community and effective technology transfer
- encouraging public understanding of the environment

NERC is one of a number of organisations within the United Kingdom supporting environmental research, survey and monitoring. NERC's emphasis on basic and strategic science is complementary to and integrated with the more applied work of government departments and agencies such as the Environment Agency, Department of the Environment, Overseas Development Administration, Ministry of Agriculture Fisheries and Food, Department of Transport.

1 Summary

Environmental Directions summarises the result of extensive consultation with the Natural Environment Research Council's (NERC) scientific and user communities. The **Introduction** sets the scene by identifying the six **Environmental and Natural Resource Issues**. The **Scientific Challenges** reflect the views of our scientific community on the exciting areas of their science for the next five to ten years. The views of NERC's diverse user community are reflected in the **Environmental Foresight Topics**: technological opportunities and markets that will grow or emerge in the next 10-20 years. These elements can be linked together to show how exciting basic science will ultimately contribute to environmental and economic competitiveness.

2 Introduction

Environmental Directions is a summary of two extensive consultations carried out over a six-month period in 1995, involving scientists in Universities, in NERC Centres and Surveys and members of NERC's diverse user community.

The scientific community was asked to identify the "key scientific challenges": the topics or areas of research which hold the most promise for the next five to ten years. The resulting set of ten challenges is described in the section entitled 'The Scientific Challenges'. Each one indicates a broad area of research, giving a flavour of the current and future issues of importance. These challenges build on the science strategy documents for atmospheric, earth, marine, terrestrial and freshwater, and polar sciences published by NERC within the past two years.

In the summer of 1995, NERC set up the **Technology Foresight Implementation Group**, consisting of scientists and users, to analyse the newly published reports of the 15 panels of the national Technology Foresight Programme. The group distilled conclusions related to the environment and natural resources from all 15 panels. From this distillation, the group identified topics in which research is linked closely with emerging market opportunities and user needs. These **Environmental Foresight Topics** are

summarised in the section on 'Meeting User Needs'.

One of the principal objectives of the national Technology Foresight Programme was to generate a dialogue between researchers and users of research in order to understand better how basic science might be exploited. The path to exploitation is not a simple linear transfer of knowledge to application: basic understanding may arise as a result of trying to solve practical problems, whilst the application of a piece of basic understanding may arise in quite unexpected ways.

Illustrative linkages between the key science challenges and the foresight topics are shown in the section entitled 'Building the Connections'. Readers may wish to draw their own pathways for other Scientific Challenges and Environmental Foresight Topics. One way to draw these connections is through the principal **Environmental and Natural Resource Issues** on the UK and NERC's agenda: biodiversity; environmental risks and hazards; global change; natural resources; pollution; waste.

These six issues are likely to be of increasing importance in decades ahead as human impacts upon the environment and its resources increase through population and economic growth.

Global change

Global change and its relationship with regional environmental management are potentially the most significant long-term environmental issues. The composition of the Earth's atmosphere is changing. The causes include human activity, such as burning of fossil fuels which releases approximately five billion tonnes of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere each year. It is increasingly probable that the changes in atmospheric chemistry are associated with changes in the global climate, a view now supported by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. Understanding environmental change, its interactions with pollutants and its impacts, both globally and regionally, is thus essential for planning future strategies for response and for assessing the urgency of the need for action.

Biodiversity

Loss of biodiversity is of global and local concern. Estimates of current global rates of extinction are between 1000 and 10,000 times greater than the 'background rate' in the fossil record. The need for action, recognised in the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity, results not only from the moral considerations of irreversible damage to species and habitats, but also from practical and economic factors relating to the unpredictable environmental consequences of loss of the genetic resource of biodiversity.

Waste

Each individual in the UK produces six tonnes of waste per year. The issue of waste disposal and its environmental impacts has potential implications for human as well as environmental health. Past disposal, or accidental release, of toxic waste has left a heritage of contaminated land for which remediation techniques are needed.

Natural resources

The key natural resources for the UK include both non-renewable resources such as oil, gas, minerals, sand and gravel, and renewable resources such as water, living marine resources and forests. Management of land and coastal zones to meet conflicting demands of urbanisation, agriculture and other forms of exploitation and conservation is also a key aspect of sustainable use of our natural resources.

Pollution

Pollution of the atmosphere at ground and higher levels is of growing concern in relation to both immediate effects on human health and longer term effects on global climate. Understanding the factors that influence the quality of land, rivers, lakes, groundwater, coastal zones and the oceans is the key to reducing impacts on the environment and enhancing industrial efficiency to meet legal and regulatory requirements.

Environmental risks and hazards

Understanding and predicting the character of natural earth processes which present a hazard to human health and the environment (such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, land instability, storms and floods) will help to solve problems relevant to human safety, planning and insurance. Developments in biotechnology are leading to the use of genetically modified organisms for agriculture, medicine, environmental improvement and regulation (eg detection of wildlife crime). Their environmental hazards need to be fully understood, so that risks can be minimised.

3 *The Scientific Challenges*

The challenges underline the increasing emphasis on understanding the connections between components of the environment: coupling of oceans, atmosphere and ice, the feedback between living and non-living, the reciprocal impacts of human activity on the environment and its resources.

The need to understand global change provides a focus for many fundamental questions - the nature of global biogeochemical cycles, the resilience of ecosystems, the dynamics of ice sheets. Although studied in the context of global change, these questions pervade all aspects of the basic understanding of the environment.

There are two general themes, which are in themselves major scientific problems but which also cut across many of the individual challenges. These are the issues of spatial scale and of linkage between social and environmental sciences.

Whilst many of the key problems in environmental science refer to large scale processes in space and time, much of the research effort is focused on mechanisms that operate on small, short-term scales. The challenge is to link small-scale processes to outcomes at the larger scale of catchments, regions or continents, and vice versa. Indeed, the distinction between local, regional and global processes is one that is increasingly difficult to sustain.

An illustrative example is current theoretical understanding of storms and other extreme weather events, which is based on the fluid mechanics and thermodynamics of large systems. Observations of

velocity, pressure, temperature and water content of the atmosphere, made from aircraft, balloons and radar, show that the dynamic changes in the atmosphere include a rich pattern of small-scale events. The numerical techniques necessary to assimilate the fine scale observations into large-scale dynamics are currently being developed.

Other examples include the extrapolation from the demographic and behavioural processes that influence populations on a local scale to the explanation and prediction of abundance on a regional scale; the linkage between the impact of pollutants on individual organisms and effects at the ecosystem level; and understanding long-term erosion rates of continents from local measurements and models.

It is increasingly apparent that the practical use of basic knowledge of the environment and its resources often involves bringing together environmental sciences and socio-economic considerations. Widely used concepts such as "sustainability" and "total economic value" require an ability to incorporate environmental considerations into the analysis of economic costs and benefits using an appropriate currency. Although methods for doing this already exist, there are still fundamental questions to be resolved, such as the dynamic feedback between human action and the state of the environment, before fully satisfactory decision support systems can be developed to inform policy makers.

The challenges are arranged in alphabetical order.

Characteristics of the atmosphere

The changes in chemical composition of the atmosphere currently taking place

are thought to be caused largely by human activities. The principal greenhouse gases, carbon dioxide, methane (from waste dumps, livestock, rice paddies, the fuel industry and other sources) and nitrous oxide (from fuel burning, the chemical industry, animal wastes and soils) are predicted to contribute to global warming. Understanding the chemical reactions that determine the levels of the gases, and the influence of non-uniform distribution on the reactions, are major challenges for atmospheric chemists.

The "ozone hole" - the reduction of ozone in the upper atmosphere (stratosphere) - is known to be caused in part by chemical reactions involving CFCs (chlorofluorocarbons). However the role of other chemicals and their relative importance is still a key question, as is understanding the extent of the

Data from satellites

A key advantage of observing the surface of the planet by satellites is that it enables, for the first time, accurate

measurements over the whole surface of the globe at frequent intervals and over long time periods. A particular feature is its "synoptic" quality which allows large areas to be imaged or measured at virtually the same time - an impossible task by airborne- or ground-based systems. An example is the measurement of global sea surface temperature over many years to within half a degree Celsius.

Satellites detect radiation in the visible, infra-red and microwave ranges. The exact pattern of radiation reflected and radiated by the surface of the land or water bodies depends on both chemical and

ozone hole in both polar and temperate regions.

One of the major uncertainties in the prediction of future climate change is the role of clouds and other aerosols in the radiation balance of the Earth and atmosphere. Aerosols are suspensions of fine particles in the atmosphere some of which are natural, eg dimethyl sulphide, and others are man-made, eg sulphur dioxide.

The radiation balance of the Earth depends on the amount of energy arriving from the sun and the amount of energy radiated from the Earth out into space. Clouds may have either a warming or a cooling effect, since they both reflect back radiation from the Earth's surface and block incoming radiation from the sun. The magnitude of these effects depends on physical factors such as water droplet size and proportion of ice in the clouds. The challenge is to combine observations of radiation from space, and measurements from airborne platforms, with modelling of cloud structure to develop an understanding of how clouds influence radiation budgets.

physical properties of the body. For example the infra-red pattern reflected by plants depends on the biochemical properties of the leaves, the plant's shape and the angle of radiation striking the plant. The situation is even more complex in a multilayered structure such as a tropical rainforest.

A major challenge is to understand and model patterns of radiation so that satellite data can be used to identify different kinds of land and water surface. The challenge is not only to gather and interpret, but also to handle, process and visualise large quantities of data.

Satellite data will make an increasingly important contribution to understanding global change, to documenting human influence on the environment, and to resource management.

Dynamics of the Earth

The evolution and nature of the Earth are ultimately determined by climatic processes

on its surface and by the energy generated at much greater depth. The internal forces largely determine the geochemistry of the land surface and of the oceans, the location of many resources, the character of the landscape and its evolution, the nature and variation of the magnetic field and the frequency of volcanic events and earthquakes which can have a devastating impact on human society.

A major challenge is to provide the basic geological, geophysical and geochemical understanding of how the internal engine of the planet works on the global scale in terms of heat dissipation, melting and flow. To do this, it is necessary to understand the mechanisms of slow convection in the layers of the mantle (extending down below the thin solid crust to almost half the radius of the Earth), the origins of melting and magmatism (production of new molten

rock) and of the pathways and rates by which mantle fluids reach the surface. These processes determine the movements of the plates that form the Earth's surface and generate earthquakes and volcanoes. Understanding the Earth's internal processes requires new methods of acquiring and interpreting deep geophysical data, from seismic, geodetic, geo- and electro-magnetic methods, geochemical evidence from rocks which formed at depth, from experiments in the laboratory as well as construction and testing of 3-D models of the crust and the deep interior. Another challenge is to investigate and understand the origin and variation of the Earth's internally produced magnetic field which is responsible for the generation of the Earth's protective magnetosphere.

The key to solving these major problems may lie in understanding the nature of the boundary between the mantle and the core, core chemistry and whether the magnetic field is generated by currents flowing in the metallic outer layer of the core.

Evolution, biodiversity and ecological roles

Current estimates of the total number of species on the planet range from

3 to 30 million: an indication of the overall need for further documentation of biodiversity, especially of less well-known groups and habitats.

Among the techniques that have revolutionised the study of biodiversity, molecular methods are prominent. Gene sequences have resulted in new understanding of evolutionary relationships at both the large- and small-scale. At the large-scale of classification, for example, the bacteria have been shown to contain two fundamentally distinct groups. At the level of species, estimates of the time of evolutionary divergence of the earliest hominids from the great apes have been radically altered as a result of molecular data. Theoretical methods now

allow the construction of evolutionary trees from molecular data. Newly emerging techniques allow past rates of birth and death of species to be inferred from these trees.

Knowledge of biodiversity and its evolution underpins the analysis of interactions between different species in ecological communities. Questions concerning the degree to which assemblages of species or species types within communities can be predicted or are essentially a matter of chance are still unresolved. Molecular probes are being used to reveal new information about the ecological roles of micro-organisms that have been traditionally difficult to study in the environment. These include microbial populations that may underpin the major biogeochemical cycles in the oceans; bacteria and fungi that play important roles in energy and nutrient fluxes in soils; and micropathogens that cause disease in natural populations.

Fluid flow through rocks and soil

Many questions in the earth sciences require an understanding of the

processes controlling the flow of fluids through rocks and sediments. These processes, including stress, fluid pressure and permeability, can be studied using theoretical techniques, by experiments on a small scale in the laboratory and through fieldwork including remote geophysical monitoring. These include the rise of molten rock through the lithosphere, the expulsion of aqueous fluids from sedimentary basins and the flow of water beneath ice sheets. They are also of great importance in many practical problems such as efficient extraction of water and oil from fractured rocks, the possible seepage of radionuclides from deep waste

repositories and detecting the pathways taken by dispersing pollutants nearer the surface.

Lack of uniformity in the physical and chemical properties of rocks and fluids may have an important influence on flow, but this is not well understood and requires further research. In some situations, fluid flow involves three phases: solid, liquid and gas; adequate models to predict flow in these cases are still being developed. The effects of surface physics and chemistry in understanding how fluids are involved both in dissolving and precipitating solid material is also an area of active theoretical and experimental development. But perhaps one of the greatest challenges is to understand the role of microbial influences on fluid chemistry in the crust, and the effect these have on fluid/rock interaction, and how in the future microbial methods may be used to clean up polluted ground-waters and soil.

Global biogeochemical cycles

Many chemical elements, (eg carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and

sulphur), are distributed throughout the whole 'Earth System' of atmosphere, freshwater, land, oceans and in living or dead organisms. Although some of the broad principles governing biogeochemical cycling are understood, there are still major gaps in knowledge of the distribution of elements among components of the Earth System and the processes that determine changes in their distribution through time. The impact of human influence on the major biogeochemical cycles is now apparent, but considerable uncertainty exists over the rates of interaction and global feedbacks in the system.

For example, understanding the carbon cycle is essential for explaining and predicting change in levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide. Measurements of global carbon flux have suggested that there is a

very large amount (at least a billion tonnes per year) of carbon unaccounted for. This 'missing carbon' is being sought by careful mass balance assessments of production and respiration in both terrestrial and marine biospheres, and through studies of the ratios of carbon isotopes, since these are taken up differently by vegetation and by the oceans.

Experimental approaches include enrichment of the oceans with iron both to test the hypothesis that the availability of iron may limit the growth of marine plants, and to quantify carbon uptake and flux through the upper ocean.

Impacts of environmental change and stress

The increase in the level of carbon dioxide in the

atmosphere over the past 200 years is affecting ecosystems. For example, the production of plankton in the top 100m of the oceans may be changing. Other aspects of global change may also have important effects on biological systems in the future. What effect will there be from higher levels of ultra-violet radiation getting through a thinned stratospheric ozone layer? Local changes, for example as a consequence of pollution, can also have major impacts on living systems.

The effects of environmental change on living systems may be complex and counterintuitive, with unexpected feedbacks. For example, global warming may allow northern forests to expand. The dark vegetation (which absorbs more incoming light and

heat than snow or ice) may create a feedback loop and amplify the effects of global warming. There is a need for environmental change to be studied both theoretically and experimentally at the level of both communities and their components, and at a range of scales from the laboratory to the field.

The distribution and abundance of populations is expected to change as a result of global and local environmental change. Such changes need to be understood and anticipated, because of their effects on agriculture, conservation and disease.

Understanding will arise in part from research on the factors limiting the geographical range and movement of species. Individual organisms respond to environmental change and stress at the genetic, developmental, physiological and behavioural levels. These individual responses need to be linked to population and ecosystem responses to predict the short- and long-term impacts of change. It will be important to consider the impacts of change in the context of both human socio-economic activity and the physical and chemical processes that cause change.

Oceans, atmosphere and ice

The ocean and atmosphere exchange heat, momentum, mass (including water vapour, carbon dioxide, dimethyl

sulphide) and energy across their common interface. These transfers influence the 'weather' in both systems and contribute in a major way to the global climate and its variability.

A current challenge is to link models of the physics and chemistry of the oceans with corresponding models of the atmosphere. The atmospheric models deal with processes that occur at more rapid rates than those in the oceans, so the coupling is not straightforward. The successful coupling of models of the oceans (including sea ice) and the atmosphere will lead to more accurate prediction

of climatic changes.

Within models of the oceans an important emphasis is on describing and predicting fine scale physical changes, such as eddies, to understand how these small scale features influence the large scale movements that determine climate and weather. Accurate measurement of small scale features is also a priority to provide data to test models and to understand the underlying processes that are included in the models.

The terrestrial ice sheets and glaciers of the polar regions both contribute to, and are affected by, global climate; uncertainties in their behaviour represent the largest unknown in predictions of future sea level. The development of robust predictive models of the response of ice sheets, ice caps and glaciers to climate variability and change is a priority.

Past environmental change

A 'fossil record' of past climate is trapped in sediments on the ocean floor and in ice sheets. This

record is uncovered by measuring the ratios of oxygen isotopes in ice cores and ratios of oxygen and carbon in sediment cores from the ocean floor. Over the last 20 years this study has extended the record of past climate many tens of millions of years into the past. The results have shown that climate and atmospheric composition have altered rapidly, over periods of decades to centuries, particularly during the past 100,000 years. Future scientific challenges will include extending these records further into the past and distinguishing between past changes that were local, regional and truly global. Can these changes be explained by current models of global climate? The record of past climate

provides both a method of testing our current understanding of global processes and acts as a benchmark against which the current changes, thought to be largely caused by humans, can be judged.

The last four to five million years is particularly important for the emergence of *Homo sapiens*. The record of this period, in greater detail, provides the basis for analysing the relationship between climate change and the evolution of human morphology and behaviour.

Improved accuracy of established dating methods and development of new techniques, such as those based on the generation of isotopes of helium and neon in surface rocks by the action of cosmic rays, are leading to exciting new research. They offer the prospect of major advances not only in geology and landscape evolution, but also in palaeoecology and archaeology.

Population change and persistence

Natural populations change in abundance with time. Understanding the causes of population change is important for

conservation of declining populations, for predicting and controlling disease or pest outbreaks. It is also valuable for anticipating the effects of human intervention - for example habitat destruction and fragmentation - and for evaluating the consequences of the release of genetically modified organisms into the environment.

Theoretical and empirical studies of population dynamics will continue to be influenced by consideration of the way in which non-linear dynamics leads to fluctuations. Spatial aspects of interactions between populations or individuals, of

the same and of different species, are being modelled and studied experimentally, leading to greater understanding of how multispecies steady-states are maintained. The role of evolutionary adaptation, for example in plant-herbivore, host-parasite and mutualistic interactions, in influencing population dynamics is increasingly appreciated.

Within a species populations frequently exist as interconnected subgroups. This is especially striking where human intervention has led to extreme fragmentation and isolation of habitat patches, as for some species of butterfly in the UK. A central question is how the persistence of a population relates both to the processes within each subgroup and to the mixing of subgroups. Understanding will come from a combination of theoretical analysis, field experimentation, and the use of molecular or other techniques to quantify population structure and migration.

4 Meeting User Needs

In addition to sponsoring and carrying out the highest quality science, NERC ensures that its portfolio is connected to the needs of its diverse user community. The public, European, national and local government, educators, industry and commerce are all users of NERC research.

One approach to forming the links between basic research and its application is the national Technology Foresight Programme, which brings together scientists, engineers and users in networks and partnerships to help identify emerging opportunities in markets and technologies. Against the backdrop of the national

Fifteen Environmental Foresight Topics have been identified

INDUSTRY-ENVIRONMENT INTERACTION: to assist industry better to manage the possible impact of its operations upon the environment. User sectors include chemical, construction, manufacturing, materials, agriculture, energy industries.

ENVIRONMENTAL VALUATION: to develop a process which brings together social and economic values of different aspects of the natural environment from the viewpoint that the environment is a national asset. User sectors include construction, chemicals, manufacturing, agriculture, energy, environmental industry, small- and medium-sized enterprises and local authorities.

LAND AND SOIL: to define and understand better the relationship between land use and soil processes to provide a basis for reducing and reversing adverse consequences of human behaviour. User sectors include agriculture, leisure, chemicals and materials, retailing, insurance, local authorities, and those concerned with potential uses for wasteland (eg financial sector).

URBAN ENVIRONMENTS: to develop predictive models incorporating different environmental and economic aspects of the urban system to enable decisions on priorities for alternative plans of action. User sectors include transport, construction, health, and local and central government.

PREDICTION OF EXTREME ATMOSPHERIC EVENTS: to understand and possibly predict extreme atmospheric events to aid risk reduction in affected areas of the economy. User sectors include planning and risk reduction groups in food, finance and insurance and the Meteorological Office.

MECHANISMS OF CLIMATE CHANGE: to describe and understand the nature of climate change and predict its likely impact on people and the contribution of human activity to climate change. User sectors include transport, materials and those involved in land use including local and central government.

FLUID DYNAMICS IN NATURAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: to understand the interactions between fluids in the ground and rocks leading, for example, to increased recovery of oil and gas from known reservoirs. User sectors include oil and gas, water and waste disposal.

COASTAL ZONE MODELLING AND MANAGEMENT: to develop predictive models for use in coastal zone management including coastal defences and coastal zone remediation. User sectors include leisure, construction, transport, agriculture, fisheries and local authorities.

programme, NERC has undertaken its own survey of user needs and has initiated its own Foresight exercise. In consultation with the science and user communities, 15 Environmental Foresight Topics have been distilled from the national programme and NERC's own survey. These topics encapsulate

user needs, the science required to meet these needs and the user sectors upon which the topics impact. In many instances NERC will be able to bring these topics together with scientific challenges in research programmes. Other topics may be developed through LINK programmes and similar initiatives.

led by NERC's Technology Foresight Implementation Group

STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF THE EARTH'S SUBSURFACE: to improve imaging of the Earth's substructure with a view to enhanced recovery of subsurface resources including oil and gas. User sectors include hydrocarbons, nuclear energy, waste and water.

USE OF NATURAL PROCESSES AND MATERIALS: to improve exploitation of naturally occurring materials, both inorganic and organic, as a basis for new drugs, adhesives etc. User sectors include health, materials, manufacturing and environmental industries.

SUSTAINABLE USE OF MARINE RESOURCES: to improve understanding of the relationship between marine life, ecosystem stability and sustainable use of marine resources including wild fish populations. User sectors include fisheries, food and government.

OCEAN CIRCULATION: to develop realistic ocean circulation models, to understand the impact, dispersion and fate of pollutants. User sectors include chemical and pharmaceuticals, food and electronics sector (for instrumentation for data collection).

REMOTE DATA ACQUISITION: to gather high quality environmental data as a basis for modelling and predicting the environment particularly with respect to human impact and improved management of environmental impacts. User sectors include insurance, energy, leisure, environment industry, government and many others.

SOCIAL AND HUMAN HEALTH IMPACTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGE: to understand better the links between human health and the environment. User sectors include health, transport, leisure, high environmental impact industry, government.

MANAGEMENT OF FRESHWATER RESOURCES: to improve scientific tools for the sustainable management of freshwater resources, including the supply of potable water. User sectors include chemicals, manufacturing, extractive and water industries, and the environmental industry.

Scientists for the Future

One of NERC's most important contributions to wealth creation and quality of life is the education and training of scientists, required to sustain environmental R&D in the science base and industry. NERC is meeting this demand through a range of opportunities: Advanced Course Studentships, Research Masters Training Awards, Research Studentships, CASE (Cooperative Awards in the Sciences of the Environment) and Industrial CASE Studentships, Research Grant Tied Studentships and Career Fellowships.

5 Building the Connection: Issues, Challenges and Topics

There are obvious and, perhaps, some less apparent connections between the Environmental Foresight Topics, the Scientific Challenges and Environmental and Natural Resource Issues. The illustration below shows how connections can be drawn between the challenges, issues and topics. The arrows connecting the boxes are two-way, because impetus could start in any of three sectors. An example of one of the

inter-relationships is highlighted in bold type. By providing this example, we hope the reader will be encouraged to think of how other Scientific Challenges and Environmental Foresight Topics connect and how both fit into the overall framework of the six Issues. Turning these connections into reality will in itself be a challenge for both scientific and user communities in the years ahead.

The International Dimension

The environmental sciences cross national boundaries and much of NERC's research is carried out within an international framework of:

- agreements with other countries, agencies, institutions and programmes;
- selective participation in international scientific programmes (eg. Ocean Drilling Program);
- hosting Project Offices for international programmes, such as the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme and World Climate Research Programme;
- membership of the International Group of Funding Agencies which coordinates global change research activities at the agency level;
- bilateral links with space agencies of other countries, working through the European Space Agency and other international agencies;
- taking a prominent role in international Antarctic affairs through the British Antarctic Survey, and collaborative work with the national agencies of the circum-Arctic countries;
- exploiting the full range of European Union opportunities, including prominent roles in developing Framework research programmes and as an active partner and coordinator;
- pursuing an active role in development of a European science strategy through the European Science Foundation, the European Heads of Research Councils, the European Science & Technology Assembly, and the NATO civil science programmes; and
- contractor and adviser to the Overseas Development Administration.

Environmental Directions is a snapshot: inevitably perceptions will evolve. Furthermore, it does not attempt to cover every aspect of NERC science and technology: in condensing the scientific challenges and Foresight Topics to very short summary statements, much important detail is hidden between the lines. Environmental Directions, which is written to be intelligible to the non-specialist but representative of the views of the scientific and user communities, should be treated as a framework for the future.

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